

HUMORAL IMMUNE RESPONSES IN CATTLE VACCINATED WITH RECOMBINANT Bm95 AND LOCAL

Boophilus microplus WHOLE EXTRACT ANTIGEN

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Abstract

Eighteen healthy experimental cattle were divided into three groups (A, B and C) of six animals in each. They were about 2 year's age having no previous exposure to ticks. They were selected from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi (Jharkhand). Engorged adult *Boophilus microplus* female ticks were reared for the preparation of Local *B. microplus* larval whole extract antigen (BmWEAg) in laboratory and tick challenge infestation. Bm95 recombinant tick antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad. Group A and B were inoculated with 1 ml of Bm95 (200µg protein/ml) and 1 ml of BmWEAg (250µg protein/ml) respectively intramuscular on zero day and second dose in the same amount on 15th day after primary dose whereas group C kept as an unvaccinated control. All animals were challenged with 100 unfed larvae of *B. microplus* reared in laboratory on day 30, day 70 and 120 day post immunization (DPI). Humoral Immune Response as indirect ELISA test was recorded at maximum level (ELISA) on 90th and 60th day post vaccination in Bm95 and BmWEAg groups of the animals.

Key words: Bm95 recombinant antigen, *Boophilus microplus* antigen, Humoral immune response, Tick larval and Tick challenge.

Introduction

The cattle ticks *Boophilus microplus* (*Rhipicephalus microplus*) are the most common blood-sucking arthropods that spread haemoprotozoan diseases like Theileriosis, Babesiosis and Anaplasmosis etc., among cattle and buffaloes (Cafrun *et al.*, 1995). Tick infestation causes significant economic losses in the world especially in tropical and sub-tropical countries. These losses can be controlled by reducing tick population. There are many conventional methods to control the population of ticks. Out of several conventional methods, chemical method is more appreciable among all these (Martins *et al.*, 2002). The vaccines contained the recombinant *B. microplus* Bm86 gut antigen. Two such vaccines using recombinant Bm86 were subsequently registered in Latin American countries (Gavac, Heber Biotech S.A., Havana, Cuba) and Australia (TickGARD, Hoechst Animal Health, Australia) during 1993–1997. These vaccines were found to reduce the number of engorging female ticks, their egg laying and reproductive capacity. Thus, the greatest vaccine effect was the reduction of larval infestations in subsequent generations. In the controlled field trials, these vaccines in combination with acaricide treatments demonstrated that an integrated approach in control of tick infestations and reducing the use of acaricides. These trials demonstrated that control of ticks by vaccination has the advantages of being cost-effective, reducing environmental contamination and preventing the selection of drug resistant tick's that result from repeated acaricide. Very recently, Argentinean Bm86, renamed Bm95 (only two amino acid changes) by the Cuban group, formulated into a vaccine has been tried by the Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad with highly encouraging results. Keeping these in mind, the present investigation was planned to assess the Humoral immune responses in cattle inoculated with both the immunogens, Bm95 and BmWEAg by measuring Indirect ELISA response against *B. microplus* infestation in cattle.

Materials and methods –

The present study was carried out on eighteen healthy cross bred cattle calves of about 2 years age and having no previous exposure to ticks. They were selected and segregated from Instructional Bovine Farm, RVC, Kanke, Ranchi. Engorged adult female ticks (*Boophilus microplus*) (Fig-1) were collected from naturally infested cattle herds in and around Ranchi. They were washed and placed in B.O.D. incubator at temperature 28 ± 10 °C and relative humidity (R.H.) 85 ± 5 %. After oviposition, larval emergence were used for the preparation of antigens and challenged on experimental animals.

Bm95 recombinant vaccine- Bm95 recombinant tick antigen was obtained from Indian Immunological Ltd., Hyderabad. As per the details provided by the supplier, the source of the antigen was *B. microplus*. Briefly, Bm95 (*Boophilus microplus*), which is a concealed

tick gut antigen and final protein concentration in the formulated vaccine was 200µg/ml.

Local *B. microplus* larval whole extract antigen (BmWEAg)- The larval antigen was prepared as per the standard method (Vanden *et al.*, 2003) with minor modification. One gram laboratory reared local *B. microplus* (7-8 day unfed) larvae were thoroughly cleaned by washing for 5 minutes in ice cold Phosphate Buffer Saline (PBS), PH 7.2 by mixing one percent Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate at room temperature and then washed 10 times in ice cold PBS and finally sonicated in ice cold PBS. The homogenate were centrifuged at 10,000 Xg for 10 minutes. The protein concentration (Lowry *et al.*, 1951) of supernatant antigen (Ag) mixed with Freund's complete adjuvant was 250µg/ml. Experimental cattle were divided into three groups (A, B and C) of six animals in each. Group A and B were inoculated with the first dose of 1 ml of Bm95 (200µg protein/ml) and 1 ml of BmWEAg (250µg protein/ml) respectively intramuscular on zero day and the second dose in the same amount of respective antigens on 15th day after primary immunization whereas group C were kept as controls.

Indirect enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (indirect ELISA)

Humoral immune response against both antigens (Bm recombinant antigen and BmWEAg) were measured by employing Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay using sera samples collected from animals before and after immunization. For standardization the standardized method used was as that of Law *et al.* (1996) using Bm95 antigen. In this case BmWEAg antigen was also used. Flat bottom, high binding capacity microwell ELISA plates from Greiner, Germany were used for the test.

Wells of microtiter plates were coated with 100µl of each antigen (4µg protein/ml of buffer). The coated plates were incubated over night at 4°C and were washed thrice with washing solution (0.1M PBS containing 0.05% Tween-20) and then air dried. Wells were then blocked with 200 µl of coating buffer (5% skimmed milk powder in 0.1 M PBS containing 0.1% Tween-20). The plates were then incubated at 37°C for 2 hrs. Again plates were washed thrice with washing solution. Then 100µl diluted pooled test serum (1:10 to 1:20480) from the calves of each group were added to wells of microtiter plates and the plates were incubated at 37°C for 2 hrs. Thereafter, serum was removed and the plates were washed four times with washing solution. Then 100µl of 1:7500 diluted anti-bovine IgG HRPO conjugate was added to each well and plates were incubated at 37°C for 2 hrs. Once again the plates were washed four times with washing solution. The plates were then air dried and 100µl of substrate solution containing 30mg OPD (Orthophenyl diamine) in 50 ml phosphate-citrate buffer and 40µl 30% H₂O₂ was added. The plates were allowed to stand for 30 minutes at room temperature under subdued light. 50µl of stop solution (4N

H₂SO₄) was added to each well and the absorbance values were recorded at 492 nm in ELISA reader (BioRaid, USA).

The antibody titers were calculated by using the following formula:

$$\text{Log Ab titer} = X - \frac{A - C}{A - B} \times D$$

Where, A is the A₄₉₂ of the test sample dilution immediately higher than the cut-off A₄₉₂ value, B is the A₄₉₂ of the test sample dilution immediately lower than the cut-off A₄₉₂ value, C the cut-off A₄₉₂ value [Cut off value is the mean A₄₉₂ of the negative samples (n=16) + 3 S.D.] D is the log dilution factor; X is the log dilution of the test sample having A₄₉₂ immediately higher than the cut-off value.

Fig.1 Engorged adult female ticks.

Indirect ELISA test were conducted on day 0 after that 20 days interval up to two months then monthly interval next 4 months. For the assessment of Humoral immune responses of both the antigens, all animals were challenged with larval ticks on day 30, 70 and 120 DPI with unfed larvae. These larvae were released on both the ears (50+50) of each cattle and ears were covered and tied with cloth ear bags (Fig.2). All the vaccinated and unvaccinated cattle were subjected to humoral immune response before and after immunization at monthly interval up to 6 months. Test of significance among the groups using two-way analysis ANOVA was done and by using Win STAT (2003) software system.

Fig 2: cattle challenged with *B. microplus* larvae.

Results and Discussion

For the assessment of humoral immune response, pooled sera samples collected from Bm95 and BmWE_{Ag} and unvaccinated animals were subjected to Indirect ELISA on different days of observations. The values of ELISA titer of all the three groups of animals have been shown in Table no. 1. The anti-Bm95 antibody titer in Bm95 vaccinated animals was 185.33±2.85 on 0 day and 6361.47±221.00 on 90th day (Fig. 3) then a significant (P<0.01) reduction in antibody titers was observed on 120th day (4895.70±267.01) and on 180th day

(1466.32±144.77) post vaccination and challenge infestation as mentioned in Table no. 1. Similar observations have been reported by Rodriguez *et al.* (1995), Andreotti (2006) and Kumar *et al.* (2009). The present study revealed a significant increase in anti-Bm95 antibody titer which might be due to formation of antibody which provided immunity in vaccinated animals against tick infestation. Rodriguez *et al.* (1995) reported that there is a direct correlation between the anti-Bm95 antibody titer of vaccinated calves and its effect on feeding

Table no. 1: Status of Indirect ELISA titer in calves on different days before and after vaccination and challenge.

Groups (No. of animals)		A (6)	B (6)	C (6)
Nature of vaccine		Bm95	BmWE _{Ag}	Unvaccinated
Before vaccination	0 DAY	185.33±2.85 ^a	183.75±2.65 ^a	186.6±1.67 ^{ab}
Post vaccination	20 th day	^C 912.57±38.02 ^b	^B 625.4±40.56 ^b	^A 183.2±3.05 ^a
	First challenge on 35 th day	40 th day	^C 2582.83±52.64 ^c	^B 1185.47±46.18 ^{de}
60 th day		^C 5516.43±325.32 ^f	^B 1337.26±66.97 ^e	^A 190.62±2.28 ^{bc}
Second challenge on 70 th day	90 th day	^C 6361.47±221.00 ^g	^B 1188.57±41.00 ^{de}	^A 188.53±1.05 ^{ab}
Third challenge on 120 th day	120 th day	^C 4895.7±267.01 ^e	^B 1135.39±85.01 ^d	^A 190.57±3.11 ^{bc}
	150 th day	^C 3637.92±207.55 ^d	^B 908.95±31.81 ^c	^A 196.68±1.37 ^c
	180 th day	^C 2466.32±144.77 ^c	^B 762.94±64.06 ^{bc}	^A 188.5±1.63 ^{ab}

Values having the same superscripts in column (small) and row (capital) did not differ significantly and reproductive parameters. Garcia-Garcia *et al.* (2000) also lowering the number of ticks. Further, they observed that Bm95-based vaccine was also able to protect the cattle against Bm86-resistant ticks. Significant level of protection by

Bm86 antigen has been reported by Willesden *et al.*, (1989); Rodriguez *et al.*, (1995); Fragoso *et al.*, (1998) and Andreotti (2006).

Anti- BmWE_{Ag} antibody titer in BmWE_{Ag} vaccinated animals ranged from 183.75±2.65 on 0 day to 1337.26±66.97 on 60th day post vaccination, i.e. day 30 post first challenge (Fig.4). However, there was

a mark reduction in antibody titers from 90th day (1188.57±41.00) to 180th day (762.94±64.06) post vaccination and challenge infestation. The rise in antibody titer was statistically significant (P<0.01) from 20th day to 180th day post vaccination. However, a significant (P<0.01) drop in titer was also observed from 90th day to end of the observations as shown in Table no. 1. In case of unvaccinated animals, the antibody titer was significantly (P<0.05) increased from 0 day (186.60±1.67) to 150th day (196.68±1.37) post vaccination and challenge as shown in Table no. 1. Similar observations have been reported by Rodriguez *et al.* (1995), Ghosh and Khan (1996) and Andreotti (2006) using different tick- derived antigens. In the present study, a significant increase in anti-BmWEAg antibody titers was observed which might be due to protective antigens were found in BmWEAg immunogen.

In case of unvaccinated animals, the antibody titer was significantly (P<0.05) increased from 0 day (186.60±1.67) to 150th day (196.68±1.37) post vaccination and challenge (Table no.1). Similar observations have been reported by Njau and Nyindo (1987). The present study revealed a slight rise in anti-tick antibody titers which might be due to formation of antibody which provided acquired immunity by repeated tick infestation.

Conclusion

The humoral immune response was found at maximum level (ELISA) on 90th and 60th day post vaccination in Bm95 and BmWEAg groups of the animals as compared to control animals.

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